

PROGRESS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF COST-EFFICIENT MMCs WITH SELECTIVE CONTINUOUS FIBER REINFORCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

The use of CFRMs (Continuous Fiber Reinforced Metals) is currently restricted particularly due to inadequate fiber and processing costs. The application of filament winding techniques and cost-efficient casting routes open up new possibilities to surmount these limits. As a necessary requirement composites have to be developed with both, high strength in the fiber reinforced and non-reinforced conditions. The paper reports on the suitability of conventional as well as adapted aluminum alloys for use as matrices of CFRMs. Tensile strength in longitudinal and transverse direction, elastic modulus and strain-to-failure of test specimens made with a 50% 'Altex' fiber reinforcement have been measured and compared to the properties of the non-reinforced alloys. With appropriate matrices mean UTS values of about 740 MPa in longitudinal and 220 MPa in transverse direction have been produced. Al-Cu and Al-Zn-Mg alloys are suggested as highly appropriate to match the intended spectrum of properties. Examples of potential applications with a selective fiber reinforcement are given.

INTRODUCTION

Merely some decades ago steel was almost the only material used for structural applications. Today design engineers have the choice of a broad spectrum of metals, ceramics and polymers with considerably varying properties. The selection is particularly influenced by technical performance, costs and, recently becoming more and more important, reusability of materials and their products, respectively. New developments are driven by the objective to design materials with a property spectrum most suitable for specific applications.

With respect to their technical performance, the group of metal matrix composites (MMCs) have the potential to find a broad spectrum of applications. Owing to their high performance to weight ratio, there is high interest particularly in light alloys with embedded continuous ceramic fibers which offer extremely high strength and stiffness. Current restrictions on the application are attributable chiefly to inadequate cost-effectiveness of available processing technologies and high fiber costs.

A significant drop of fiber costs is not expected in the near future. Therefore, a considerable reduction of materials costs seems to be feasible only by using a smaller amount of fibers. Real structural components usually show highly as well as less stressed regions. The latter need not necessarily to be strengthened. Therefore, selective reinforcement techniques become more and more important for technical applications.

Necessary requirements for selectively fiber reinforced components are sufficiently high strength and stiffness of the matrices used. Pure aluminum yields very high strength when reinforced with continuous fibers and is, therefore, mainly used in CFRM (Continuous Fiber Reinforced Metals) research [1, 2, 3]. Due to low strength in non-reinforced regions, however, it is not appropriate as matrix for composites with a selective fiber reinforcement. Alloyed aluminum matrices, which exhibit at least moderate tensile strength, need to be employed. Research on CFRM should, therefore, aim on good mechanical properties both, in the reinforced and non-reinforced conditions.

The paper reports on results of an European Brite/EuRam research project on the development of cost-efficient CFRM-based components for structural use. Subsequent to the development of an appropriate process technology, research is actually focused on the optimization of material properties and realization of small fiber reinforced components.

EXPERIMENTAL: PROCESSING BY INVESTMENT CASTING

Specimens have been produced by a newly developed precision casting process. The production technique is based on investment casting which is well established for manufacture of high-quality components primarily for the aerospace sector. Main benefits of the investment casting process are high design freedom, near-net-shape production and cost-efficiency for small to medium series numbers. In comparison to the conventional technique, certain modifications have been made in the pattern manufacture and casting substeps, see flow chart in **Figure 1**. High design flexibility is ensured by employing filament winding techniques known from fiber reinforced polymers. Infiltration of the molten aluminum into the fibers is supported by inert gas pressurization. Besides various test specimens some small to medium sized components for demonstration of the load transfer or stiffening capability have been produced until now. With respect to real applications, the modified investment casting process seems to be suitable for an economic and flexible production strategy and thus, could allow CFRMs to be used for a broader spectrum of industrial applications.

Fig. 1: Flow diagram of the modified investment casting process for production of CFRM parts. The wax pattern fabrication substeps can be combined with flexible filament winding techniques [4].

PRELIMINARY SELECTION OF MATERIALS

With respect to the hardening mechanisms two types of alloys can be distinguished: precipitation hardenable and solid solution hardenable alloys. The certain type is characterized by the solubility of the alloy elements in solid aluminum. Alloys containing elements whose equilibrium solubility in aluminum decreases with decreasing temperature below their nominal concentrations precipitate in form of secondary phases. Owing to this highly efficient hardening effect almost all technical Al alloys used for structural applications belong to this group, like Al-Si, Al-Cu, Al-Mg, Al-Zn-Mg-Cu and Al-Li alloys. With an appropriate heat treatment tensile strength in castings reaches up to 420 MPa [5].

In contrast, solid solution hardenable alloys are composed of element whose concentrations do not exceed their equilibrium solid solubility. Zn and Mg are the elements with highest solid solubility in aluminum, see **Figure 2**. Cu shows a considerably lower solubility, and most elements like Si or Fe are almost insoluble. In ternary and higher alloyed systems the presence of third elements can further reduce the equilibrium concentrations due to the formation of new phases. Examples are the $MgZn_2$ and Mg_2Si phases that are less soluble than Mg in the binary alloy. Solid solution hardenable alloys therefore usually contain low element concentrations. The hardening effect of solid solutions is usually lower as compared to precipitations. Maximum tensile strength reaches up to about 250 MPa [5].

Phase precipitations play a decisive role in the mechanical behavior also of continuous fiber reinforced Al. In contrast to the monolithic alloys, however, precipitations in CFRMs have a harmful influence on strength. As examples, comparably low composite strength was reported on SiC fiber reinforced Al-Si-Mg [2], Al_2O_3 fiber reinforced Al-Cu [6] and Al-Li alloys [7].

The approach of a selective fiber reinforcement of aluminum castings requires both, high strength in the reinforced and at least medium strength in the non-reinforced conditions. Minimum goals of 600 MPa and 200 MPa were aimed at for the project work reported. For investigation of the influence of the matrices and their phases a number of aluminum alloys of both groups, precipitation and solid solution hardenable, as well as pure aluminum were used. In a first step conventional cast alloys were used including Al-Si (AA356), Al-Mg and Al-Cu (AA201) alloys. In order to eliminate the influence of alloy impurities, binary and some ternary alloys mixed from pure elements (99.98%) were used in a second step. Elements with none or low solid solubility like Si and Cu were used as well as Zn and Mg with higher solid solubility. Element concentrations were varied between 1% and 5%. For all castings the alumina-silica fiber 'Altex' was used as continuous fiber material, see **Table 1**.

Fig. 2: Solubility of alloying elements in solid aluminum in dependence on temperature [5].

Table 1: Composition and main properties of the Altex continuous fiber of Sumitomo Chemical [3].

	Altex SN
Chemical Composition	85% γ - Al_2O_3 , 15% SiO_2
Fiber Sizing	none
Fiber Diameter [μm]	15
Tensile Strength [MPa]	1800
Elastic Modulus [GPa]	210
Strain to Failure [%]	0.86
CTE [$10^{-4} \cdot K^{-1}$]	N/A.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: COMPOSITE PROPERTIES

LONGITUDINAL TENSILE STRENGTH

Tensile tests in longitudinal fiber direction were carried out with round test specimens. The specimens have 4 mm in diameter with a parallel length of about 15 mm. A minimum of 4 tests were carried out for each alloy type used, however, most values given below are mean values of more than 10 tests.

Insufficient low tensile strength values have been measured for composites with the conventional precipitation hardenable casting alloys as matrices, **Figure 3**. In the non-reinforced condition these alloys offer high strength above the aimed value of 200 MPa. With a fiber reinforcement, however, their strength could not significantly be increased up to the intended value of 600 MPa. The AA356 and Al-5%Mg alloys show an only slightly improved UTS, and with the AA201 matrix even a lower strength was measured for the composite than known from the non-reinforced matrix alloy.

Fig. 3: Ultimate tensile strength of conventional high strength cast alloys both, reinforced with about 50 % of Altex fibers and non-reinforced. Values for the non-reinforced matrices are given for heat treated castings taken from literature [5, 8]. The minimum goals of 600 MPa (reinforced) and 200 MPa (non-reinforced) are marked in the diagram.

The matrix alloys selected in the second step of the investigations are composed of lower alloy concentrations including Zn and Mg that offer highest possible solid solubility. Owing to the less efficient hardening mechanism these alloys have a lower UTS in the non-reinforced condition as compared to the conventional alloys used in the first step. With additions of Cu or Zn and Mg, however, the intended matrix strength of >200 MPa can be achieved, see **Fig. 4**.

In the fiber-reinforced condition strength was considerably improved for all alloy types used. With *pure Al* as matrix a high composite strength of 737 MPa was measured which is slightly lower than comparable literature values obtained by squeeze casting [3]. The composite with *Al-2%Si* matrix suffers from unfavorable Si precipitations located at the fiber surfaces resulting in a lower UTS of 495 MPa. Compared to AA356 composites, however, strength is higher due to the lower amount of secondary phases. The *Al-1%Mg* matrix alloy is free of precipitates and produces a very homogeneous fiber distribution. The free Mg content, however, has been detected slightly to attack the alumina-silica fibers leading to a reduction of tensile strength as compared to pure Al. Best results not only in the non-reinforced, but surprisingly also in the reinforced condition, have been measured for *Al-2%Cu* and *Al-5%Zn-1%Mg* alloys. The mean values of 738 MPa and 749 MPa, respectively, comply with the intended minimum of 600 MPa. Both alloys produce only a very small amount of precipitates. Due to the high solubility in liquid aluminum these phases are formed in the solid state and are, in contrast e.g. to Si crystals, very fine and homogeneously distributed within the matrix.

Fig. 4: UTS values of low alloyed and solid solution hardened alloys both, as non-reinforced matrix and reinforced with 50% Altex fibers. The minimum goals of 600 MPa (reinforced) and 200 MPa (non-reinforced) are marked in the diagram. Values for the non-reinforced matrices are given for heat treated castings taken from literature [5, 8].

Figure 5 shows cross sections and fractographs of composites with both types of matrices, precipitation and solid solution hardened alloys. The differences in the microstructure clearly appear in the optical micrographs. In the Al-4%Cu-Ti-Mg alloy the spaces between the primarily solidified dendrites are filled out with the secondary eutectic phase containing Al_2Cu . As the fibers are pushed during solidification by the growing dendrites, they also concentrate within the interdendritic spaces. The secondary phase crystals now act as bridges between fibers and fiber groups and are thereby responsible for the unfavorable single fracture mode, see fractograph of the Al-5%Mg alloy which has a comparable microstructure. In contrast, Figure 5 additionally shows composites made with matrices almost free of precipitations. Owing to the single-phase microstructure of the matrix the fibers are distributed more homogeneously, see Al-1%Mg matrix. The absence of bridges between the fibers allows branching of cracks during propagation resulting in a favorable multiple fracture mode, clearly visible in the fractograph of the Al-7%Zn alloy.

TRANSVERSE TENSILE STRENGTH

Transverse tensile strength has been measured with flat specimens separated from bigger sheets. The measurement length is about 10 mm with a cross section of $2 \times 7 \text{ mm}^2$. A minimum of 3 tests were performed with each matrix alloy. A minimum goal of 100 MPa was set initially. Transverse UTS results are shown in Figure 6. Insufficient values were measured with pure Al and Al-3%Cu matrices. Specimens of the latter suffered, however, from a large number of non-infiltration defects. With the conventional AA357 as well as the Al-1%Mg alloy sufficiently high transverse strengths of about 120 MPa were obtained. The Al-4%Zn-1%Mg alloy even produced an extraordinary high mean value of 219 MPa.

Comparisons of the test results with the microstructures of the specimens show a different role of the matrix material as compared to the properties in longitudinal direction. Transverse composite strength is particularly influenced by the strength of the matrix itself and by the interface. Secondary phases do not significantly reduce transverse strength. The presence of processing defects like non-infiltration voids have more harmful effects.

Fig. 5: Polished cross sections (top) and fracture surfaces (bottom) of Altex fiber reinforced aluminum alloys. **Left:** Precipitation hardened alloys with secondary phases (Al_2Cu -phase precipitations and Al-5%Mg alloy with a single fracture mode. **Right:** Solid solution hardened alloys nearly free of precipitations. Al-1%Mg and Al-7%Zn alloy with multiple fracture mode.

Fig. 6: Transverse tensile strength of pure Al and different aluminum alloys reinforced with 50% Altex fibers. The minimum goal of 100 MPa is marked in the diagram.

ELASTIC MODULUS AND STRAIN-TO-FAILURE

The elastic moduli of the composites have been calculated from the stress-strain curves taking the three stages into account that are typically measured with CFRM composites. In the first stage both constituents, fibers and aluminum, deform elastically. At the flow strength of the matrix, plastic deformation starts while the fibers' deformation remains elastic. In the third stage both materials deform plastically [9]. In the experiments, mainly the first two stages could be detected. Only with a few combinations showing higher strain-to-failure, a third stage was measured. The measured E values of both stages show only slight dependence on the matrix alloy. For the first stage values ranged between 104 (Al-Mg) and 118 MPa (Al-Zn and Al-Si matrices), for the second stage between 85 (Al-Si) and 94 MPa (Al-Cu). Strain-to-failure values, however, showed a more significant influence of the matrix used. Plastically high deformable matrices result in highest strain of the composites. Maximum values were in the range of 0.8 to 0.9 % with pure Al, Al-Zn or Al-Cu matrices. Lowest strain-to-failure of 0.27 % was measured for composites with an Al-4%Mg matrix, probably caused by the formation of brittle interface products.

POTENTIAL APPLICATIONS

Owing to its high design flexibility and cost-efficiency the investment casting route opens up new possibilities for the use of light weight metal matrix composites. Advanced CFRM materials with a combination of excellent mechanical properties seem to be highly appropriate for structural and engineering applications with high requirements on load transfer and stiffness in static and dynamic conditions. Groups of potential end-users are the aeronautics, sports and leisure, mechanical engineering, and automotive industries, see **Figures 7 and 8**.

Fig. 7 (above): Examples of potential airplane applications of aluminum alloys with selective fiber reinforcement: Primary aileron rip fitting, reinforced for the load transfer through the component (left), and gear box, reinforced for stiffening of bearings (right), [10].

Fig. 8 (left): Feasibility study of a selectively fiber reinforced frame segment, produced by investment casting.

CONCLUSIONS

The results described show the possibility to design CFRM composites with a combination of both, good mechanical strength in longitudinal and transverse fiber direction as well as in non-reinforced areas. The investment casting process employed has the capability to produce fiber composites with a high efficiency as compared to theoretical values. The choice of the matrix alloy, however, has a strong influence on properties, see **Table 2**. Conventional casting alloys like AA357 are not appropriate for achieving high composite strength in longitudinal direction. The development of new aluminum alloys for use as matrices is necessary. Promising candidates are solid solution hardenable alloys like low alloyed Al-Cu or Al-Zn-Mg matrices as suggested above. The favorable character of these composite materials opens up new possibilities in the selective fiber reinforcement of aluminum castings. With strength values of more than 200 MPa transverse to the fibers and in non-reinforced areas, these types of MMCs could match requirements of structural applications that are not possible with fiber reinforced polymers [11].

Table 2: Efficiency of the experimental tensile strength and elastic modulus in relation to theoretically calculated values according to the simple rule of mixture (for 0°-properties) and in comparison to the matrix ultimate tensile strength (90°).

Matrix Alloy	Density [gcm ⁻³]	UTS (0°)	E-Modulus (0°)	UTS (90°)
AA356/AA357	2.78	33 %	86 %	46 %
Al pure	2.70	79 %	79 %	109 %
Al-2%Cu	2.82	72 %	78 %	N/A.
Al-4%/5%Zn-1%Mg	2.91	73 %	83 %	91 %

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